

Predictive Cognitive
Maintenance Decision
Support System
PreCoM

Predictive Cognitive Maintenance Decision Support System

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Scheduling Model Report (I): Definition of Predictive Maintenance Information

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Executive Summary

The PreCoM project

Cheaper and more powerful sensors, predictive cognitive CBM system, together with big data analytics, offer an unprecedented opportunity to track machine-tool performance and health condition. However, manufacturers only spend 15% of their total maintenance costs on predictive (vs reactive or preventative) maintenance.

The PreCoM project will deploy and test a predictive cognitive maintenance decision-support system able to identify and localize damage, assess damage severity, predict damage evolution, assess remaining asset life, reduce the probability of false alarms, provide more accurate failure detection, issue notices to conduct preventive maintenance actions and ultimately increase in-service efficiency of machines by at least 10%.

The platform includes 4 modules: 1) a data acquisition module leveraging external sensors as well as sensors directly embedded in the machine tool components, 2) an artificial intelligence module combining physical models, statistical models and machine-learning algorithms able to track individual health condition and supporting a large range of assets and dynamic operating conditions, 3) a secure integration module connecting the platform to production planning and maintenance systems via a private cloud and providing additional safety, self-healing and self-learning capabilities and 4) a human interface module including production dashboards and augmented reality interfaces for facilitating maintenance tasks.

The consortium includes 3 end-user factories, 3 machine-tool suppliers, 1 leading component supplier, 4 innovative SMEs, 3 research organizations and 3 academic institutions. Together, we will validate the platform in a broad spectrum of real-life industrial scenarios (low volume, high volume and continuous manufacturing). We will also demonstrate the direct impact of the platform on maintainability, availability, work safety and costs in order to document the results in detailed business cases for widespread industry dissemination and exploitation.

Goal and structure of the deliverable

The present document *D4.1 Scheduling Model Report (I): Definition of Predictive Maintenance Information* is a public deliverable of the PreCoM project, developed within *WP4: Production Planning & Maintenance System Synchronization* at month 7 (May 2018). Maintenance is transforming due to new technological advances in the fields of sensors and communication. This enables the concept of *Predictive Maintenance (PdM)*, where imminent failure of the machine can be predicted. Using this information, production can be scheduled in such a way that the probability of failure will be reduced. Furthermore, maintenance and production can be synchronized in order to increase machine availability. This deliverable describes the general approach of how PdM input information can be retrieved and characterized. It covers all information parameters that constitute the target parameters (see D3.1 for more details) needed for PreCoM, for example information parameters needed for the modules/technologies building PreCoM. It also covers the output information that provided to the end-user by different the different modules. It then focuses on what information is needed and how it should be dimensioned in order to plan maintenance actions and production schedules.

List of acronyms

CM	Condition Monitoring
CMMS	Computerized Maintenance Management System
eMDSS	eMaintenance Decision Support System
D	Deliverable
MOO	Minutes of Operation
PdM	Predictive Maintenance
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

Maintenance has, as well as the whole industry, evolved during the past decades. The image of maintenance has changed rapidly from cost creating to a value adding process, since correct and efficient maintenance can increase machine availability – and thus the overall equipment efficiency – substantially (Strunz 2012). In order to correctly maintain machine tools, engineers have gone from preventive, i.e. scheduled maintenance, to conditioned based and Predictive Maintenance (PdM) (Bellias 2017). As a key driver for Industry 4.0, PdM utilizes embedded sensors; wireless connectivity and big data analytics to detect communicate and assess attritions of machine components. Furthermore, PdM derives recommendations for maintenance actions and their schedule based on attritions and predicted remaining lifetime of a critical component. This reflects the overall objective of the project PreCoM. In the project, three different use cases are addressed, each with its own particularities: low volume manufacturing, high volume manufacturing and continuous production. In order to fulfil this task, target parameters and the derived information from use case companies have to be described in detail. For the development of work package (WP) 4 as a whole, it is thus crucial to properly define the retrieved PdM information in such a way that it can be utilized for production and maintenance scheduling optimization.

Figure 1 depicts the simplified information flow relevant for WP4 work. From the use case target parameters that are described in D3.1, information parameters are derived for the stress model, production scheduling and maintenance optimization model. The stress model will be based on statistical and physical models developed in WP3, which will be refined in D4.2 in order to provide a product specific stress model. As such, this deliverable will focus the maintenance and production scheduling information.

The information of the stress model will be used by production scheduling, which will schedule production according to customer demand and so that machine failure can be avoided. According to the production schedule, maintenance optimization will plan a maintenance schedule that will maximize machine availability.

Figure 1: Information flow of WP4 work.

As such, the objectives of this deliverable are as follows:

- a) Characterization PdM-input and output information
- b) Methodology for PdM-information retrieval
- c) Information parameters of Use Case companies
- d) Introduction of required information for maintenance and production planning

First, the general concept of PdM-information is given and a methodology is described for how this information will be retrieved. Next, the demonstration use cases are presented briefly and the targeted critical components are described with respect to the information gathered. The information parameters of the use case companies then are derived from the specified target parameters of WP33. They are described and their means of retrieval are shown. The approach to production and maintenance scheduling is introduced next and their information requirements are given. Predictive Maintenance Information

1.1. Characterization of PdM-Information

Nowadays, manufacturing industry is exposed to increasing national and international competition. Therefore, they try to increase their marginal through developing new technologies, tools and methods to reduce economic losses that are generated due to lack of or ineffective maintenance (Al-Najjar 2007; Lee et al. 2014). Effective maintenance activities have a positive impact on profitability (Maletic et al. 2014; Al-Najjar & Algabroun 2018). Different branches in industry experienced that PdM especially when using vibration spectral analysis is a reliable tool for maintaining machine reliability and improving its availability (De Azevedo et al. 2016). PdM is necessary to reduce the probability of failure and unnecessary stoppages, which in turn reduces production cost through prolonging production time and increasing production. In WP4, PdM information provided by the WPs leading up to WP4, in particular the information processed by WP3 will be used for optimally scheduling production and maintenance. This section focuses the characterization and the retrieval of PdM information. PdM information is understood as the information, which enables us to predict the residual life (or MOO, minutes of operation) of a specific machine component, as well as the predicted residual life itself with its corresponding probability distribution.

We consider the necessary PdM-information as a mean to fulfill the end user's requirements in reducing the risk of failures and unnecessary stoppages, prolonging production time in order to reduce production cost and improve company profitability and competitiveness (Al-Najjar 2007).

This information should:

1. Describe the current condition of the machines in consideration to maintain production continuity.
2. Be easily accessible for users.
3. Be provided continuously and on demand.
4. Be presented in a pedagogic way, i.e. easy to read, understand and follow up.

1.2. Methodology of PdM-Information retrieval

The PdM information that we consider fulfilling the end-user's requirements should include the information necessary to map the current conditions of the machines targeted, possible

development in the near future, estimation of residual life and recommendations of the proper maintenance actions. To achieve this, the PdM information should express:

1. The damage detection if there is any.
2. The location of the detected damage, i.e. in which machine and component.
3. The assessment of the severity of the detected damages.
4. The prediction of the damage development in the near future.
5. Estimation of residual life and failure probability.
6. The recommendations of actions to take and where.
7. Sending work order to actuator for conducting automatic action.
8. Sending diagnosis/prediction/recommendation report to maintenance department for the rest of the tasks that are not automated yet.

At the end of the project, PreCoM should be equally applicable for old and new machines. In both cases the significant components (components whose failure is expensive or dangerous) of a machine should be identified for PreCoM application.

In order to evaluate PreCoM application in every demo-machine, specific data is necessary to be gathered for visualizing the impact of PreCoM. Therefore, to provide PreCoM with this information to conduct its functions, we follow a top-down systematic analysis found in Al-Najjar (2012) for problems of selected demo companies' machines and components. This analysis is necessary to be performed at first to identify the problems/failures that are already experienced in the machine targeted. This is to specify the components that will be monitored and to specify what techniques, methods, condition monitoring (CM) parameter(s), measuring frequency and tools should be implemented to avoid re-occurrence of the same failures/problems.

The steps below describe the followed top-down analysis to identify and describe the necessary information to accomplish PreCoM tasks in diagnosis, prediction, activation of AR and actuators, reports, work orders, etc.

- (1) Specify demo-company and use cases that are targeted**
- (2) Specify demo-company machines that will be monitored**
- (3) Specify machine problems/failures from past data**
- (4) Specify the components suffered of these problems**
- (5) Specify the root-causes behind these problems/failures/damages**
- (6) Identify failure modes and deterioration process**
- (7) Identify appropriate information, CM sensors, and communications**
- (8) Gathering of measurements**
- (9) Analysis-diagnosis-prognosis process**
- (10) Recommendations associated with each measuring/diagnosis-prediction opportunity**

More details about the required information is described below:

1. Demo-company production and use cases targeted in PreCoM will be introduced.
2. Demo-company machine will be introduced.
3. The machine selected should have had stoppages and/or failures that can be prevented in the future by using a new technology, such as PreCoM. Thus, it is

necessary to have the total number of stoppages and failures per year or month based on the machine past data and personnel experience.

4. We will specify and describe the components (e.g. bearings, shafts, gearwheels, etc.) suffered of these problems/failures. The description is preferable to be in text, photos and technical drawings if exist.
5. Then, we will identify the probable root-causes behind these problems/failures/damages, such as construction faults, misuse, severe operating condition, bad quality maintenance actions and normal deterioration.
6. Next, we will identify failure modes and experienced deterioration processes, for example severe wear, fracture and corrosion.
7. Thereafter, it will be possible to identify the information/data needed as well as CM sensors.
8. The data will be gathered with the support of identified sensors.
9. When data is gathered, the output of the analysis-diagnosis and prediction will normally lead to output data, for example description of the machine condition, work orders and recommendations that should be sent to relevant machine, personnel/departments.
10. The recommendations for production scheduling and maintenance actions will be addressed using maintenance optimization module. It will be based on production planning and product specific stress models. Maintenance optimization module aims to reduce the number of stoppages demanded by several maintenance strategies, such as preventive maintenance (time based), breakdowns and urgent maintenance, for more details see D4.2.

Steps 1-6 have been conducted in WP7 (cf. D7.1, D7.3 and D7.5), steps 7-9 will be the focus of WP2 and 3. Step 10 will be targeted in WP4 (cf. D4.2, D4.3).

2. Demonstration Companies - Information of Use Cases

Over the course of the PreCoM-project, the methodology described in section 1.2 will be applied on three different Use Cases:

1. Soraluca's machines installed at Sakana, a European reference in the wind sector. In particular, wind turbine hubs are produced.
2. Overbeck's machines installed at SPINEA, which manufactures gear components.
3. Papermill located at Goma-Camps, which manufactures and sells tissue paper products.

For detailed information about the use case companies and their machines, refer to D7.1, D7.3 and D7.5. In the following section, the information parameters, which derive from the target parameters described in D3.1 (see Figure 3), will be shown use case specific. These information parameters will be used to further derive the needed information of maintenance and production scheduling, shown in the sections afterwards.

Figure 2: Target parameters and their relation to components and information parameters, as seen in D3.1.

2.1. Sakana use case

The Sakana factory produces components for wind turbines, namely hubs, under a automated production-scheme in a low volume manufacturing setting, i.e. job production. In addition, Sakana offers an integral service within the same facilities and everything managed by the group's own companies. shows the targeted machine and its critical component, the spindle head.

Universal spindle head

Universal head
37 / 46 kW
2.5° x 2.5° / 1° x 2.5° / 0.001° x 0.001°
3000 / 4000 / 5000 / 6000 rpm

Orthogonal spindle head

Orthogonal head
37 / 46 kW
1° x 1° / 1° x 0.001°
4000 / 6000 rpm

Figure 3: Critical components of SAKANA use case. Top: Wind Hub part, Bottom: universal and orthogonal spindle head.

The following table shows the identified target parameters, their relation to the use cases and the general input parameters that will be retrieved for the aforementioned production and maintenance optimization algorithms.

Table 1: Target parameters and information parameter of Sakana Use Case

Target Parameter	Information Parameter	Targeted significant component	Means of information retrieval
Machine and Component General Information	Targeted Machine ID	All	Soraluce FXR Milling Boring Machine
	Targeted Component ID	All	Rotating Components (Motor, Spindle Head, Gearbox), Feed Drive, Tool
Condition Monitoring Information (Basic Variables)	Temperature	Feed Drive	Machine Control
	Vibration	Spindle Head	Max. 9 mm/s for machining operation (based on expert knowledge), retrieved by accelerometer.
	Acceleration Speed	Feed Drive, Spindle	Speed: Retrievable by Machine Control
	Process Force	Tool, if information is available	Not retrievable at the moment

	Product being manufactured	Not applicable	retrievable from the part program name of the CNC
	Specific operation/task	Not applicable	Retrieval via Machine Control
	Noise	Not determined yet, if required	If required, noise sensor connected to controller
	Load	Motor, Feed Drive, Spindle	Retrieval via Machine Control
Failure and Machine Stoppage Information (Time Variables)	Failure Dates	All	Retrieval via OLANET MES, recorded via Excel Sheets, see D7.1
	Failure Type	All	Recorded via Excel Sheets, see D7.1
	Stoppage Date	All	Retrieval via OLANET MES, recorded via Excel Sheets, see D7.1
	Stoppage Reason	All	Recorded via Excel Sheets, see D7.1
Production and maintenance related information (Production and maintenance Variables)	Production Costs	Not applicable	KPI Excel sheet, see D7.1
	Maintenance Costs	All	KPI Excel sheet, see D7.1
	Maintenance Plan/register	All	KPI Excel sheet, see D7.1
	Quality of produced items	Not applicable	Scrap Rate; KPI Excel sheet, see D7.1
	Duration of product specific machining operation	Not applicable	Retrieval via OLANET MES or Savvy Cloud
Predictive Maintenance Information	Remaining Useful Life	All/most critical	Rotating Components: retrieval via Smart EMDSS Feed Drive, Tool: Time Series analysis and Life Time Analysis
	Failure Probability	All/most critical	Rotating Components: retrieval via Smart EMDSS Feed Drive, Tool: Time Series analysis and Life Time Analysis
	Acceptable Threshold of critical values (e.g. failure probability, vibration level at failure or replacement ...)	All/most critical	User Given or derived by data

2.2. Spinea use case

Spinea possesses two factories for the high volume production of gears components and the final set of precision reduction gears. PreCoM will focus on Overbeck ID-400 high precision grinding machine, cf. Figure 4.

Figure 4: Overbeck ID-400 high precision grinding machine.

However, Spinea currently does not possess any machine from Overbeck. The grinding machine will be installed in week 38 of 2018. Spinea indicated that the main critical components are the the four wheelhead spindles, the workhead spindle, and the dressing spindle, the linear axis. As such, the following table is a preliminary state:

Table 2: Target parameters and information parameters of Spinea use case.

Target Parameter	Information Parameter	Targeted significant component	Value/Description/means of retrieval
Machine and Component General Information	Targeted Machine ID	All	Overbeck ID-400
	Targeted Component ID	All	Spindles (workhead, wheelhead, dressing), grinding spindles, linear axis
Condition Monitoring Information (Basic Variables)	Temperature	Linear axis	Retrievable by Machine Control
	Vibration	Spindles	Accelerometer (connected to controller)
	Acceleration/speed	Spindles	Speed: retrievable by Machine Control
	Process Force	If available, Tool	To be defined
	Product being manufactured	Not applicable	Different Gear parts, retrievable from the part program name of the CNC
	Specific operation/task	Not applicable	CNC
	Noise	To be defined	If required, noise sensor connected to controller
	Load	Spindles	Retrievable by Machine Control
Failure and Machine	Failure Date	All	
	Failure Type	All	

Stoppage Information (Time Variables)	Stoppage Date	All	Manual retrieval in Excel file, see D7.3 for examples
	Stoppage Reason	All	
Production and maintenance related information (Production and maintenance Variables)	Production Costs	Not applicable	
	Maintenance Costs	All	
	Maintenance Plan/register	All	
	Quality of produced items	Not applicable	
	Duration of product specific machining operation	Not applicable	
Predictive Maintenance Information	Remaining Useful Life	All/most critical	To be defined
	Failure Probability	All/most critical	To be defined
	Acceptable Threshold	All/most critical	User Given or derived by data

2.3. Goma-Camps use Case

The Gomà-Camps Group has two paper machines in La Riba’s mill, equipped with Lantier’s creping systems for the production of 100% virgin cellulose tissue and recycled tissue, with a total capacity over 60,000 Mt/per year. In a previous project, a monitoring system was installed in the creping doctor of the machine TM5. In PreCoM, machine TM6 will be connected and monitored too. shows a general overview of the Goma Camps paper mill. The critical components identified in this use case are the yankee gearbox, yankee dryer roll itself, two E-motors and the suction press roll, cf. Figure 5-Figure 6. To maintain the dryer system performance, the tissue manufacturer must pay special attention to the creping doctor and creping blade, the yankee dryer, the gearbox, bearing and papermaking felt among others. Consequently, the creping blade is considered to be the most important critical component and has to be exchanged frequently.

Figure 5: Overview of Goma Camps paper mill.

Creping Doctor

Blade holder

Figure 6: Creping doctor and blade holder.

Figure 7: Mounting the hood (left) of the Yankee dryer (right).

Figure 8: Suction press roll (orange, in the middle) in contact with the yankee dryer.

Table 3: Target parameters and information parameters of Spinea use case.

Target Parameter	Information Parameter	Targeted significant component	Value/Description/means of retrieval
Machine and Component (General Information)	Targeted Machine ID	All	Paper Mill No. 6
	Targeted Component ID	All	Yankee Dryer Cylinder and components related to it: creping doctor, motor, gearbox, bearings; creping blade, felt roll
Condition Monitoring Information (Basic Variables)	Temperature	Yankee Dryer	Retrievable by machine control
	Vibration	Creping Doctor	Accelerometer (connected to controller), maximum to be defined.
	Acceleration/speed	Creping Doctor	Speed: Retrievable by Machine Control
	Process Force	To be defined	Not retrievable at the moment
	Product being manufactured	Not applicable	Paper of different Qualities, manual retrieval
	Specific operation/task	Not applicable	manual retrieval
	Noise	To be defined	If required, noise sensor connected to controller
	Load	Not applicable	not available in this use case
Failure and Machine Stoppage Information (Time Variables)	Failure Date	All	Manual retrieval in Excel file, see D7.5 for examples
	Failure Type	All	
	Stoppage Date	All	
	Stoppage Reason	All	
Production and maintenance related information (Production and maintenance Variables)	Production Costs	Not applicable	
	Maintenance Costs	All	
	Maintenance Plan/register	All	
	Quality of produced items	Not applicable	
	Duration of product specific machining operation	Not applicable	
Predictive Maintenance Information	Remaining Useful Life	All/most critical	Yankee Dryer Cylinder and components related to it: retrieval via Smart EMDSS; creping doctor: Time Series analysis and Life Time Analysis
	Failure Probability	All/most critical	Yankee Dryer Cylinder and components related to it: retrieval via Smart EMDSS; creping doctor:

			Time Series analysis and Life Time Analysis
	Acceptable Threshold	All/most critical	User Given or derived by data

3. Stress model Information

The crucial information for PdM is the estimated probability distribution of the remaining operation time of the targeted machine/component. From that probability distribution, relevant parameters such as the mean residual lifetime, future probabilities of failure or stoppage, and specific quantiles of the residual life can be calculated. . The estimation of such parameters will be performed through proper statistical methods for the analysis of lifetimes or failure data (Kalbfleisch and Prentice 2011). The information parameters derived from the target parameter in section 2 (in particular *General Information, Basic Variables and Time Variables*) will be used as input information for these calculations. For more information about these calculations and input information, please see WP3 and D3.1 in particular. The output information of the stress model will consist in a product specific interpretation of residual lifetime data and probability distributions, which will be used in production scheduling. For more information about the stress model, please refer to D4.2.

4. Production scheduling algorithm (PROPTIM)

The smart PProduction OPTIMisation scheduling algorithm (PROPTIM) was developed by PARAGON under the EC project *FoFdation – The Foundation for the Smart Factory of the Future* (FP7-2010-NMP-ICT-FoF, *Grant agreement no. 260137*) [Tsahalis, J. et al]. It is a specialized tool for manufacturing environments. By design, its role is to form an integral part of a Manufacturing Execution System (MES) and to interact with other subsystems and tools. The smart aspect of PROPTIM is the generation of optimal production schedules based on triple bottom line (TBL) Sustainability metrics (economic, environmental and social factors) and is not based solely on traditional production requirements. It selects the optimal production schedule based on available schedules, sustainability evaluations, time and cost information, and any inputs needed from Life Cycle Assessment, Enterprise Resource Planning, or other tools, while working on-line using current information. In the FoFdation project, PROPTIM was demonstrated on an actual automotive component manufacturing line shop-floor of FIAT-CRF, consisting of 8 operation points and 30 machines (Figure 9). A detailed description of PROPTIM is included in Deliverable D4.2.

Figure 9: Full generalized example of PROPTIM interface model of Fiat-CRF use case shop-floor with 8 Operating Points and 30 Machines.

4.1. Information parameters required by production scheduling algorithm

For PreCoM, PROPTIM will be augmented to produce optimal production schedules based also on the predicted stresses on the machines and their critical components by the products of the work orders at hand. When applied to a specific case, PROPTIM incorporates a simulation model of the production process that is used in turn by an Evolutionary Algorithm (EA) to optimize the production schedule for the multiple conflicting constraints and requirements of the use case.

The adaptation of PROPTIM to any use case first requires a complete description of the production process in order to generate a faithful model that will then be used by the EA to optimize the production schedule. The basic information necessary is shown in the “use case production model part” of Table 4. These descriptions are mainly the layout of the production system with the number of operation points and included machines; their types and arrangement; any buffers or work-piece distribution systems; number and types of different products produced; all machine details per product produced; and any information regarding relevant worker shifts.

The EA optimization aspect of PROPTIM was designed for TBL sustainability. The information parameters required are shown in Table 4. The focus of the production schedule can be adjusted to the PreCoM requirements and the individual aspects of each Use Case. For example, social factors are not critical for the PreCoM Use Cases and can be either removed or given low priority. Production stresses will be included as defined in the project (per product and machine). It is worth noting that several of the required inputs also become outputs of the optimization due to the generation of new optimized schedules.

For each Use Case it is essential that all production related definitions (e.g. availability, performance, quality, downtime, etc.) are double-checked to be common between partners, as differences have already been observed during some factory visits.

Table 4 includes the required information parameters for generating the production scheduling optimization. In bold lettering in the table is the introduction of component stresses per product for the PreCoM project. The already included parameters are all information about work orders; any planned scheduling items; standard production metrics (e.g. OEE, availability, etc.); energy costs and efficiency; direct and indirect CO₂ production; worker absenteeism and injury rates.

Table 4: Generalized PROPTIM required information parameters covering Use Cases from single to multiple machines and products.

Use Case production model	Production layout	Drawing of the production layout
	Number of operation points (OP)	Machine groups for different operations such as roughing, finishing, etc.
	Total machines	The total number of machines in the production line taken into account
	Machine type(s)	Manufacturer(s) and model(s)
	Machine distribution	No. of machines per OP
	Buffer for each OP stage	No. of work pieces that can be held in a buffer between Ops
	Machine power consumption	In kW for each machine state (processing, ready, idle, off/standby)
	No. of different products	How many different products can be produced in the production line
	Type of different products	All differentiating aspects of products (name, type, raw material, etc.)
	Average machining time per product	In seconds, the average time required per machine to process a part. In cases of single machines handling multiple tasks, time in minutes or hours per each task
	Retooling times	In seconds, the time needed to change the machine tool.
	Conveyor delays between OP stages	In seconds, in case of multiple machines.
	Crane delays between conveyor and machine to load/unload/transfer	In seconds, in case of multiple machines.
	Average time to switch machine state	In seconds, the time to switch processing, ready, idle, off/standby
	Feed rate of raw pieces/material	The rate at which raw pieces or material are fed into the first stage of the production line
	FIFO queue arrival (λ)	Pieces per hour, the rate at which raw materials are delivered to the production line
	Total no. of pieces (daily)	Typical daily production capacity
	Shifts per day	No. of shifts per day
	No. of working hours per shift	In hours
	Lunch break/shift change duration	Duration and schedule of lunch breaks and shift changes
No. of employees	How many employees are involved in the production line	
Employee positions	The positions of each of the employees	
Production scheduling optimization	Component stress per product (PreCoM addition)	The result of the stress models providing the estimated stress on the machine's critical components from specific products
	Number of work orders	No. of work orders
	Work order product type(s)	The product(s) to be manufactured per work order
	Work order product quantity	The quantity of each product to be manufactured
	Work order requested delivery time	The requested date for work order completion
	Work order earliest/latest delivery time	The earliest and latest delivery time for the work order
	Planned stops of production line	Holidays, maintenance, the periods for which the production line will be shut down for any reason
	Starting conditions of each machine	Maintenance status of the machine and its components before production start
	Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE)	OEE = Availability * Performance * Quality
	Availability (A)	Availability = (ProductionTime / ScheduledProductionTime) *100 where ProductionTime = ScheduledProductionTime - DownTime, (metrics) and, DownTime refers to machines being Out-Of-Order, Off-Line & in Maintenance.
	Performance Efficiency (E)	Performance = DesignedCycleTime / (ActualOperatingTime / ProducedUnits)
	Quality (Q)	Quality = 100% - SR (Scrap Ratio or Pulls) or, Quality = 100% - (IrreparableUnits / ProducedUnits) *100
	Scrap Ratio	Scrap Ratio = (IrreparableUnits / ProducedUnits) *100
	Energy Cost (C)	If considered fixed: Energy Cost = EnergyTariff * Energy Consumption
	Energy Consumption (EC)	Energy Consumption (EC) = SUM (energy consumed at shop-floor / day
	Energy Efficiency (EE)	Energy Efficiency = (Default Energy for PUs / Energy Consumption)
	Saved Energy (SE)	Saved Energy = (Default Energy for PUs - Energy Consumption)
	CO2 Direct	CO2 Direct = EC_Gas * CO2DIR_Coeff
	CO2 Indirect	CO2 Indirect = EC_El * CO2IND_Coeff
	Lost Time / Absenteeism	Lost Time = (NumberOfLostTimeInjuries / TotalManhours)*100
Injuries Rates (vs Work Patterns)	5d Injuries Rate = Severe Injuries f(WorkPattern & Productivity). 1d Injuries Rate = Lighter Injuries f(WorkPattern & Productivity).	

Table 5: Generalized required information parameters with foreseen adjustments for PreCoM project.

	Required information parameters	Foreseen adjustments
Production scheduling optimization	Energy Cost (C)	Economic aspects can be related only to energy, expanded to include other parameters or limited to other specific economic parameters tailored to specific user cases. If there are no real-time metrics, static equations can be used to estimate the energy aspect.
	Energy Consumption (EC)	
	Energy Efficiency (EE)	
	Saved Energy (SE)	The environmental aspects of the production can be removed if there is no available information. If only past data is available, the metrics can be adjusted with a simple reference equation that relates specific percentages of emissions to production levels.
	CO2 Direct	
	CO2 Indirect	Social aspects of the Triple Bottom Line sustainability metrics. These metrics are typically based on a simple linear equation calculated from statistics of previous years. They allow for the proper evaluation of each schedule's impact on workers, especially when production is ramped up. If no official information is available, a simple baseline equation can be defined to help illustrate the effects of these parameters. The end user can also choose to remove these parameters altogether.
	Lost Time / Absenteeism	
	Injuries Rates (vs Work Patterns)	

4.2. Information parameters provided by production scheduling algorithm

Upon generating an optimal production schedule, PROPTIM can provide any and all necessary descriptive information of the schedule, including the relevant data listed in Table 6 for the next process in line, i.e. maintenance optimization - Smart eMDSS (Smart eMaintenance Decision Support System). The descriptive information is also used to provide a full simulation of the proposed production process. Examples of the visual representations generated by PROPTIM are given in Figure 10.

Figure 10: PROPTIM example figure of a production plan graphic indicating the status of each machine in time. The top figure shows a 5-day work week while the bottom figure shows a full 8-hour shift and the color coding for the status of machines. In both cases, the y axis indicates machines 1 to 30 and the x axis is time (in seconds but multiplied by 10 to the power of 5 and 4 respectively).

5. Maintenance Optimization

Detecting and localizing damages and prediction damage development will be conducted using Smart eMDSS (Smart eMaintenance Decision Support System). This system was developed and commercialized by Linnaeus University and e-Maintenance Sweden AB and is tested and verified in Swedish and European companies. For more details about Smart eMDSS see D3.1.

In the demonstration companies, we identified significant components in every demonstration machine (see D7.1, D7.3 and D7.5). The identified significant components are those components whose failures are expensive or dangerous. For example, spindle head in tool machines, rolling elements bearings, gearboxes, motors, drying and pressing cylinders and creping doctor will mainly be the targeted by PreCoM, see section 2.

5.1. Information required by Maintenance Optimization

Therefore, the information demanded by Smart eMDSS for detecting and localizing damage initiation, follow up damage development and prediction of the machine condition in the near future using signals from:

1. Vibration signals
2. Temperature, and in some cases
3. Acoustics,

see D2.3.

In addition, the information needed for surveying production performance and evaluating maintenance impact on production process is introduced in Table 6. The information needed is characterized by the measuring units with remarks for additional clarification to avoid misunderstanding.

In PreCoM we have three demonstration companies with well-defined and well-described demonstration, see D7.1, D7.3 and D7.5. In order to identify which information is necessary to be retrieved by maintenance optimization algorithm from every demonstration company and machine, it is furthermore necessary to determine:

1. Demonstration company name (ID),
2. Demonstration machine name (ID),
3. Maintenance strategies, policies and executive plans per demonstration company and machine,
4. Information targeted for import from maintenance/production planning systems and registers for every demonstration machine,
5. Information about the format of the imported data from maintenance and production planning systems and how it is possible to retrieve data from these systems, i.e. how to communicate with these systems, through for example Excel-files or directly with planning systems' databases per demonstration machine,
6. Information required to determine optimal maintenance point in time.

Apart from the mentioned variables, following information should also be provided in order to enable an optimal maintenance schedule with respect to production for all three use cases.

Table 6: Information for diagnosis, prediction and assessment of maintenance on production process.

Process	Information	Unit	Remarks	
Diagnosis and prediction	Installation time point	yyyy-mm-dd hr:min:ss		
	Removal time point	yyyy-mm-dd hr:min:ss		
	Vibration measurement location			
	Assessment of probability of failure and residual life	Time point for vibration measurement		yyyy-mm-dd hr:min:ss
		Mean vibration level		mm/sec
		Potential failure level		mm/sec
		Replacement level		mm/sec
		Near future load/present load		
		Prediction time period		
Assessment of maintenance impact on production	Production event start (GMT)	yyyy-mm-dd hr:min:ss	Start of production pass and of the whole period that is under study	
	Production event end (GMT)	yyyy-mm-dd hr:min:ss	Stop of each production pass & of the whole period that is under study	
	Production event type	1. Stoppage 2. Deviation of production rate	Production speed increase or reduction	
	Planned production time at the study time			
	Theoretical production cycle time			
	Actual cycle time	sec		
	Actual production quantity (accepted and rejected quality)	Measured according to company's time schedule		
	Time point for production quantity follow-up registration	yyyy-mm-dd hr:min:ss		
	Time point for user defined expenses	yyyy-mm-dd hr:min:ss		
	Expense/cost related to machine		Assessed during the whole period of the production order	
	Unique descriptive name for expenses related to machines			
	Monetary value per quantity (profit margin)		Assessed during the whole period of the production order	
	Monetary value per period (total maintenance investment)			
	Depreciation period	Periodic value		

Information concerning list of work orders:

Setup costs c_s : The setup cost describes the cost that is inflicted by machine set up; usually, production of different variants require a machine set up in between each variant and after production stops (e.g. due to machine failure or maintenance actions). The set up cost is described as a monetary unit or as a time units. The underlying question to answer in this context is: How much would it cost if a batch is not finished due to maintenance? (E.g. Is it

more cost effective to maintain the machine before producing the new batch than using the maximum residual life?)

Priority of products: Different products have different time priorities, the most urgent product that has to be shipped usually has the highest priority in production to avoid costly delays. This cost of delay c_D is important information in order to determine the point in time of maintenance and utilization of the machine, e.g. to answer the question whether a delay is acceptable if other products are produced first in order to fully use the residual life.

Information concerning machines and machine capabilities

Available machines and their capabilities: In order to determine the optimal routing of production, the information about the capabilities and availability of machines is required. In instance of a machine failure, the optimization model has to reroute production, and as thus, it is crucial to know which machine is capable of which process.

Information concerning planned maintenance stops

Information about the characteristics of planned maintenance stops are required in order to determine if those actions can be conducted in parallel. By combining multiple maintenance actions, the total downtime of a machine can be decreased and thus, the machine availability increased. For example, if a planned maintenance stop only concerns cleaning the machine, an unplanned change of a component is usually possible. Whereas if the planned maintenance stop concerns more difficult activities, another maintenance activity might not be conducted while the planned maintenance activity.

Information concerning Augmented Reality

In order to support and facilitate maintenance activities, PreCoM will use Augmented Reality technology. In WP5 and D5.1 in particular, this technology will be described in detail. The target parameters will be derived from end-user questionnaires, see D5.1, in order to ensure maximum user applicability. As such, also the necessary information parameters to conduct WP5 work will also be presented in D5.1.

5.2. Information provided by maintenance optimization

The maintenance optimization algorithm aims to optimize maintenance planning with respect to reduced number of production stoppages due to maintenance actions. The algorithm will utilize the information from production planning, i.e. production planned stoppages, and different maintenance planning systems (if there are more than one), for example preventive maintenance (time planned actions), planned actions for breakdowns and urgent maintenance, i.e. when a maintenance action is demanded based on abnormal or noisy operating machine. Therefore, the output information from maintenance optimization module will be the identification of the most suitable time to conduct all the maintenance actions suggested or needed by all different maintenance planning systems and strategies. This is to reduce the number of production stoppages and enhance machine availability.

6. Summary

This deliverable outlined a methodology of how Predictive Maintenance information can be retrieved, how it can be characterized and what specific information is needed for the work of WP4. Afterwards, the target parameters of D3.1 were detailed in use case specific information parameters. Critical components of the use case machines were briefly described. Maintenance and production scheduling are introduced and their input information requirement, as well as their outputs, are displayed. In the next step, it should be evaluated how this information can be interpreted and how it can affect production and maintenance schedules. This will be presented in D4.2.

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